

FEELINGS OF LONELINESS IN ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the problem of loneliness in adolescents. The author draws attention to the causes of this phenomenon. In addition, there are a number of factors that lead to depression.

Keywords: loneliness, depression, adolescence, personality, conflict.

One of the pressing problems of the 21st century is the tendency of some people to loneliness. In connection with the growth of cities and the number of people, a person feels less connected to society and experiences a sense of uselessness and alienation. For several decades, there was an opinion that loneliness in our society from a humanitarian point of view is impossible. However, this opinion is far from reality. Recently, scientists have begun to pay attention to the problem of loneliness among adolescents and young people, along with the problem of loneliness in the elderly.

The problem of loneliness is one of the most serious problems of humanity, in which a person, for one reason or another, is unable to establish relationships of friendship, love, or hostility. When a person feels that his relationships are not full and significant, he begins to feel even more lonely when his communication needs are not met. As a result of the philosophical and psychological analysis of the theories of loneliness, it is possible to distinguish its objective and subjective, positive and negative aspects.

The objective side of loneliness is associated with social relations and facts. The subjective side is its manifestation in connection with the characteristics of the individual. The positive aspect of loneliness is that it is an integral part of the socialization and formation of the individual. The positive potential of loneliness is manifested in such tasks as: self-knowledge, self-management, creativity, self-improvement, stabilization of psychophysical states, protection of one's "I" from external influences.

The negative nature of loneliness - it subjugates all psychic processes, violates the inner integrity of the individual, manifests itself as a psychological defense mechanism. It leads to expecting too much from those around them, to overestimating the role of others in one's self-realization as a person.

Considering the dialectical relationship between the negative and positive aspects of loneliness, it is worth noting that under certain conditions (when loneliness is understood, an active style of attitude towards it is formed, the experience of coping with difficulties is formed, and loneliness is motivated), negative loneliness can also acquire a positive significance.

The causes of loneliness in adolescence are often overlooked, arising in childhood, when the child simultaneously experiences the joy of being loved and is surprised by his own smallness and weakness. F. Fromm-Reichmann calls the

harmful consequences of premature weaning from maternal love the main cause of loneliness. The main causes of loneliness in adolescents:

1) insufficient communication with peers, low development of communication skills;

2) lack of acceptance of the teenager by others;

3) inability to assess himself and his inner world;

4) excessive demands and expectations of other people;

5) unrealistic ideas about relationships between people.

G. R. Shagivaleeva identifies the following causes of loneliness:

1) A person's conscious and purposeful desire for solitude, as well as a tendency to loneliness due to the presence of certain character traits that make it difficult to communicate with people and maintain close relationships.

2) Neglect, avoidance, forced restriction by other people, etc.

3) objective isolation as a result of a combination of circumstances.

According to foreign scientists L. M. Horowitz, R. de France and K. A. Anderson, most of the symptoms of a lonely person are almost completely repeated in the prototype of a depressive person. From this it follows that if a person is lonely, then the person shows the main symptoms of depression.

Adolescent depression is one of the most complex medical problems that can lead to suicide, violence, drug addiction, and behavioral deviations. MB Keller notes that the average age of onset of depression in patients is 14 years. During adolescence, conflicts arise between realized needs and the inability to satisfy them, as many old relationships are broken and reestablished, which leads to disappointment, depressive reactions become possible forms of psychological reactions.

Thus, analyzing the causes of loneliness is necessary for the creation of preventive measures and methods to eliminate the negative state, as well as for the formation of a socially stable, socially independent, responsible, mobile personality. Adolescence is considered the most susceptible to the emergence of various mental disorders, therefore it is important to recognize their symptoms in time and eliminate the negative factors affecting the child.

List of used literature

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